

TEACHING COMPETENCY AND MULTIPLE INTELLIGENCE AMONG PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

Veerendra Kumar¹ & Santosh Arora², Ph.D.

¹Research scholar, Department of B.Ed. / M.Ed., M. J. P. Rohilkhand University, Bareilly

²Professor of Education, Department of B.Ed. / M.Ed, M. J. P. Rohilkhand University,
Bareilly

Paper Received On 20 May 2023

Peer Reviewed On 28 May 2023

Published On: 1 June 2023

Abstract

Education plays a pivot role in strengthen of any nation. Education system depends upon the competencies of teachers teaching in the classrooms and in result they are shaping the destiny of the nation. Teaching competency is a broad term which is affected by academic, social, and psychological factors. The present paper reveals about teaching competencies and multiple intelligence of primary school teachers. The researcher also made a comparison of teaching competencies and multiple intelligence of primary school teachers based on teaching experience and professional qualifications. The method of present study is used descriptive survey method. The sample of 398 primary school teachers of district Pilibhit is selected with the systematic random sampling technique. Mean, Standard Deviation, T-test and ANOVA statistical techniques are used in the treatment of the data. This findings reveals that teaching experience do not affect teaching competency and multiple intelligence of primary school teachers. The level of multiple intelligence of primary school teachers has been affected by professional qualification, but professional qualification has not shown any influence on teaching competence.

Keywords: Teaching Competency, Multiple Intelligence, Professional Qualification, and Teaching Experience.

Abbreviations: TC - Teaching Competency, MI- Multiple Intelligence, PQ- Professional Qualification & T E- Teaching Experience.

[Scholarly Research Journal's is licensed Based on a work at www.srjis.com](http://www.srjis.com)

Introduction

Education plays an important role in social, economic, cultural and political development of the nation. It is very potential and powerful instrument to bring changes in the society. In this direction, schools are those social institutions where the future of society grows up with the

help of curriculum, teacher and methods of teaching. The role of teacher cannot be ignored in the child centered education system. Teacher is the most important molder and facilitator for students. He facilitate to students for their learning enhancement. The well prepared, competent and committed teachers are like an instrument to improve the quality of education. Various committees and commissions focused to improve the quality of education in Indian educational system. So many efforts have been taken by our government in the past to improve the quality of education (D. Dey. et al. 2015). Teachers perform in lead role to provide qualitative education. Teaching is an art and science itself because this profession faces many challenges. (Prada, M.D.M, & Gonzales, J. (2014). The fully engagement of a teacher with their students in classrooms build up their capacities, guide and motivate them, these tasks are mainly required from teacher. The success of teachers is depended upon intelligence, skills, teaching competencies, and commitment to their profession etc. (Kaur. M. and Talwar, A., 2014). In modern era, the requirements of persons, societies, and countries are varying with very high rate due to new innovations and technologies. In this context, the teachers should be engaged in teaching learning process with multiple abilities and competencies. Multiple abilities are also known with famous name ‘Multiple Intelligence’ which is proposed by a world famous psychologist Howard Gardner in 1983 in his book entitled ‘Frames of Mind’.

Theoretical Background of Teaching Competency-

In 21st century is that a competent teacher should be has firm knowledge of the curriculum of his/her subject and to use technology into the curriculum. The knowledge of content, teaching methods-techniques, teaching skills, psychological concerns, and excitement towards teaching learning process and recent technologies which helps a teacher in classrooms or outside of classrooms makes a teacher competent. The definitions of teaching competency by famous scholars are being given following-

“Teaching competency means an effective performance of all observable teacher behavior that brings about desired people outcomes.” (Passi, B.K. & Lalita, M.S. 2011).

“Teaching competency refers to the knowledge, attitude, skills and self- perception or the products that comes from by mixing these behaviour and resulting in consistent pattern of behavior leading to the attainment of expected out comes” (UNESCO ,2008).

“Teaching competency consists many dimensions such as mastery of subject matter, enhancement in motivation of student, planning, presentation evaluation, skill and classroom managerial skill (Kaur, M. & Talwar, A. 2014).

The National Council of Teachers Education has identified ten Competencies for making a teacher professionally competent. These are following-

- (i) **Contextual Competency-** In this context teacher should have the abilities to understand various contexts, such as historical background, social economic condition, cultural linguistic and religious condition of the family and the community.
- (ii) **Conceptual Competency-** In conceptual competency, teacher should have a clear thought and deep understanding of Education theories, and techniques knowledge of various educational trends, teaching methods and techniques.
- (iii) **Content Competency-** In this type of comp content competency teacher should have full knowledge on that content which they teach in classroom.
- (iv) **Transactional Competency-** In this context teacher should have full knowledge on how to recognize teaching -learning process more joyfully and activity centric.
- (v) **Educational Activities Competency-** Here the teacher should have clear thoughts on cognitive and non-cognitive area. Because both areas are equally important for organizing different activities in the school children.
- (vi) **Competencies to Develop Teaching Learning Material-** Teacher should have the ability to develop teaching aids technically for making teaching learning process more interesting.
- (vii) **Evaluation Competencies-** In this context teacher should be able to carry out continuous evaluation. An important objective of continuous evolution is diagnosis of the problems that children face in comprehending what is taught so teacher needs the ability to undertake action research.
- (viii) **Management Competency-** In this type competency teacher should have two types management skill such as within the classroom and outside classroom management skill.
- (ix) **Competencies related to working with Parents-**The role of parents are equally important for the overall development of their children. To achieve the quality of education teacher should have ability to work with parents.

- (x) **Competencies related to working with Community-** In this context, teacher should have the ability to work with the community and to use the resources of the community.

Theoretical Background of Multiple Intelligence.

The Multiple Intelligences theory was originally proposed by eminent psychologist, Howard Gardner at Harvard University in 1983 due to challenge the notion that Intelligence was a unitary general ability. He cuts across all domains of competency and brought to life a theory that proposes that there is Multiple Intelligence, (Gardner, H. 1983). Gardner defined Intelligence “a bio-psychological potential to process information that can be activated in cultural setting solve problem or create products that are of value in a culture.” (Gardner, H 1999) The seven intelligences are identified by Gardner in Multiple Intelligence theory in 1983. The two additional types of intelligence were added in multiple intelligence theory in 1999. Gardner disclosed that the two or more intelligences could be considered in multiple intelligence theory. Now the ten intelligences are considered in latest theory of multiple intelligence which are following.

- (i) **Linguistic Intelligence-** The capacity to use words effectively in oral and written in your daily life and to write grammatically correct. Such persons have excellent auditory skills. The skills of listening, speaking with fluency, reading with correct pronunciation, writing, storytelling, reorganizing information, and analyzing capacity in language uses include in linguistic intelligence. The teachers, Professors, speakers, writers, poets, and lawyers possess high linguistic intelligence.
- (ii) **Logical Mathematical Intelligence-** A person who has abilities to analyze circumstances logically, apply mathematical operations easily, arrange things systematically, and investigate issues scientifically is called number smart. In other words, such person involves detecting patterns, reason deductively and thinks logically.
- (iii) **Spatial Intelligence-** The ability to perceive the visual – spatial world accurately and to perform transformation upon those perceptions. Such persons perform better with patterns of wide space and more confined areas.
- (iv) **Bodily Kinesthetic Intelligence-** A person who have high intelligence of bodily-kinesthetic commands on own body and perform better as expert in using one’s whole body to express ideas and feeling like as actor, mime, athlete, dancer. They

facilitate in using one's hand to produce or transform things as a craft person, sculptor, mechanic, or surgeon.

- (v) **Musical Intelligence-** The capacity to perceive, discriminate, compose, and perform in musical events and patterns. It encompasses the capacity to recognize and compose musical pitches, tones, and rhythms.
- (vi) **Interpersonal Intelligence-** The ability to perceive and make distinctions in the moods, intentions, motivations and feelings of other people. These persons try to see things from other people's point of view in order to understand how they think and feel. They are skilled as emotions handlers, motivators, great organizers and manipulators. They make an effort to reach group consensus and encourage cooperation. They use open communication channels with others.
- (vii) **Intrapersonal Intelligence-** The abilities to know about himself, inner-feelings, strengths, and weakness, analyzing the desires and dreams. Such persons make their relationships with others after analyzing their desires and dreams, evaluating their thinking, patterns, reasoning with themselves, understanding their role in relationship to others. Finally they make decisions according to their inner feeling.
- (viii) **Naturalistic Intelligence-** The ability to easily recognize and classify plants, animals and other things in nature.
- (ix) **Existential intelligence-** The ability in a person to be sensitive about the world and having the capacity to think about human existence. Such a person argues about the life, death, origin of the universe and existence of any creatures.
- (x) **Spiritual intelligence -** Spiritual intelligence is the inner capacity to know about supreme power and oneself, to listen to the voice of our soul, to recognize the way of self-realization, moksha, and the seamless connection with God. Such people participate in cultural and religious programs with the belief of moral and ethical values.

Review of Related Literature

Abdel-Same & Lashmi assessing of multiple intelligence is not only important for average or above students but studies have been conducted to study the effectiveness of using a remedial strategy in light of the multiple intelligence theory developing school preparatory slow learning achievement (Aslam, A.I. 2010). Teacher competency have been categorized in nine inter-related indicators. New Mexico (USA) (2012). The study, "The relationship of Multiple
Copyright@2023 Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language

Intelligence and effective study skills with academic achievement among university study” concluded the result that multiple intelligence, study skills and academic achievement were significantly positively correlated with each other (Ayesha, B. & Khurshid, F.2013).

Singh (2015) conducted a study of secondary school teacher’s teaching competency in reference with self -perception and emotional intelligence. He found that there was no significant difference in teaching competency of secondary school teachers in reference with teaching experience.

Mishra (2017) conducted a study on the teaching competency among secondary school teachers in relation to gender subject, subject and educational qualification and teaching experience. .He found the significant difference in teaching competency of secondary school teachers in respect to gender and teaching experience.

Pratibha (2017) conducted a study of teaching competency of upper primary school teachers in central and state government school. She found that there was no significant difference in over- all teaching competency of primary school in her study.. They found significant difference in teaching competency of upper primary school teachers with regard to their teaching experience.

Chinliansiam, H. & Fanai, L. (2022) conducted a study on Teaching competency in relation to educational background and locality of students- teachers of DIET Lunglei; Mizoram. They compare teaching competency of D. El. Ed. and B.Ed. student teacher in relation to educational background and gender. They found no significant difference in teaching competency of student teachers (D. El. Ed. and B.Ed.) in regard to gender, educational qualifications.

Sivakumar, D. & Arunachalam, N. (2012).They found no significant difference in multiple intelligence in relation to gender, locality, medium of instruction, school management.

Nulhakim & Berlian (2020). found that there was significant differences in multiple intelligence with regard to gender. Male students got higher scores in compression to female students.

Need and Significance of the Study-

Education is the key of all-round development. The quality of education depends in the qualified & competent teacher. Primary education is the foundation of education. A building becomes such strong as the foundation strong. Now days, the literacy ratio has increased but our teachers & our school unable to provide qualitative education. To maintain the quality in

school institutions it is compulsory to provide basic infrastructure and facilities to the teacher. In spite of being not good infrastructure, teacher can provide qualitative education it is a based on teacher's comprise and his/ her intellectual capacity. On the basis of research findings, we can conclude that intelligence play an important/ role in effective teaching. Multiple intelligence is important factor by which he proves, more, effective, intelligent, and competent than others. in previous researches, there are a lot of research work have been done with the variable (Teaching Competency, Commitment, Job Satisfaction and Emotional Intelligence). Some other researchers have been done at degree and secondary level teacher competency. I think, Teaching Competencies are closed associated with Multiple Intelligence therefore researcher selected competency and multiple intelligence. In the present study, researcher efforts have been made to study the Teaching competency and Multiple Intelligence among government and private primary school teachers.

Statement of the Problem- The problem may be also stated as, “*Teaching Competency and Multiple Intelligence among Primary School Teachers: A Comparative Study*”

- **Operational Definition of the Key Terms**

Teaching Competency-

Teaching Competency means the group of competencies in performing their expected job. Teaching Competency includes competencies like contextual, conceptual, content, transactional, competencies related to educational activities, competencies to develop teaching learning material, evaluation, management, and competences related to working with parents.

- **Multiple Intelligence-**

Multiple Intelligence is an intellectual unity, organized with its interrelated ten intelligence areas- such as linguistic, logical mathematical, spatial, bodily kinesthetic, musical, interpersonal, intrapersonal, naturalistic intelligence, existential and spiritual intelligence.

- **Primary school teacher-** In this study, Primary school teachers mean teachers who are teaching in class 1-5 in government and self-funded primary schools, monitored by Basic Shiksha Parishad, Uttar Pradesh, Prayagraj.
- **Professional qualification-** Researcher considers B.T.C., Distance B.T.C. and B.Ed. as professional qualification in this study. These are compulsory professional qualifications to become a teacher as per state government (U.P.) rules.

- **Teaching experience**– Teaching experiences count the duration of service as primary school teacher which is classified under four category of interval e. g. (0-2 years, 3-5 years, 6-10 years and more than 10 years.)

Objectives of the Study-

1. To compare the Teaching Competencies among primary school teachers in relation to their professional qualification.
2. To compare the Multiple Intelligence among primary school teachers in respect to professional qualification.
3. To compare the Teaching Competencies among primary school teachers on the bases of their teaching experience.
4. To compare the level of Multiple Intelligence among primary school teachers with respect to teaching experience.

Hypothesis of the Study-

Ho1.There is no significant difference in teaching competencies among primary school teachers in relation to their professional qualification.

Ho2.There is no significant difference in multiple intelligence among primary school teachers in relation to their professional qualification.

Ho3.There is no significant difference in Teaching Competencies of primary school teachers with regard to their teaching experience.

Ho4.There is no significant difference on multiple intelligence of primary school teachers in terms of their teaching experience.

Design and Methodology

Population- The present study deals with primary school teachers of district Pilibhit. All the teachers of govt. and private primary schools of Pilibhit district are the population of study.

Sample and sampling technique-The multistage random sampling technique was used to select representative sample. During the first stage, Simple random sampling technique is applied to select the blocks of Pilibhit district. The three blocks (Amariya, Lalaurikhera and Marauri) were selected by lottery method out of the eight blocks of Pilibhit. After selection of 3 blocks, List of govt. and private primary schools was prepared by researcher. After it scholar arranged the name of schools in alphabetical order then applied systematic random sampling technique to select school. Each 3rd school was selected to collection of data. The total 398 primary school teachers were selected as sample of the study. Sample also includes rural & urban, male & female primary school teacher. In this study, primary school teachers were classified with special perspectives in professional qualification and teaching experience. The description of sample as per needs of study is given blow in table 1.

Table 1. Details of Sample

Sr. No.	Selection criteria		No. of Teachers	Selection criteria	
	Professional Qualification			Teaching Experience	
1	B.T.C.		133	0-2 Years	
2	Distance mode B.T.C.		74	3-5 Years	
3	B.Ed.		191	6-10 Years	
	Total		398	More than 10 years	
				Total	
				159	
				398	

Tools of the study

To carry out any meaningful research, data was gathered and hypothesis tested on the basis of tools. Selection or development of appropriate tools for research is following.

1. **Teaching Competency Scale (TCS)**, which was developed by Shukla, S. (2014) is used for data collection which is based on ten teaching competencies of NCTE. This tool consisted ten teaching competencies i.e. contextual competency, conceptual competency, content competency, transactional competency, educational activities competency, competencies to develop teaching learning material, evaluation competencies, management competency, competencies related to working with parents and competencies related to working with community.

2. **Multiple Intelligence Scale (MIS)**, To assess the multiple intelligence of primary school teachers, the researcher developed a Multiple Intelligence Scale. Multiple intelligence scale contains 10 dimensions namely- linguistic, logical mathematical, spatial, bodily kinesthetic, musical, inter-personal, intrapersonal and naturalistic intelligence, existential and spiritual intelligence which are based on Armstrong's intelligence test. The reliability of this scale is found .84 with the spilt half method.

Analysis and Interpretation

Table 2.0. Comparison on Teaching Competency among primary school teachers on the bases of their Professional qualification

T C Scores P Q	No. of Respondents		Mean	Standard Deviation	
B.T.C.	133		204.03	18.53	
Distance B.T.C.	74		200.81	19.05	
B.Ed.	191		202.76	18.74	
Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean of squares	F ratio	p value
Treatment between groups	494.18	2	247.09		
Error	138550.15	395	350.76	0.7	0.4972
Total	139044.33	397	597.85		

Table 2.0 shows scores and one way ANOVA summary table of multiple teaching competencies of primary school teachers in reference to their professional qualification. For the testing of null hypothesis researcher applied one way ANOVA. The above table depicted that the p- value of F-ratio is .4972 which is indicate $p < 0.05$ therefore the null hypothesis “there is no significant difference in the teaching competency of various professional qualified primary school teachers is being accepted. It means teaching competency of primary school teachers is not affected by professional qualifications. Chinliansiam, H. & Fanai, L. (2022) also found similar result in their study. The reason behind such findings may all teachers are treated equally in basic education department and they participated in departmental in-service trainings. The findings of this study could be effected such trainings.

Table- 3.0: Comparison on Multiple Intelligence of primary school teachers on basis of their professional qualification.

MI Score P Q	Size of Sample		Mean	Standard deviation	
B.T.C.	133		300.68	19.76	
Distance B.T.C.	74		291.88	24.16	
B.Ed.	191		301.70	23.99	
Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean of squares	F ratio	p value
Treatment between groups	5410.14	2	2705.07	5.25*	0.005620
Error	203594.93	395	15.43		
Total	209005.07	397	3220.50		

*Significant at 0.01 level of significance

Table 3.0 displays scores and ANOVA summary of Multiple Intelligence among primary school teachers with reference to their professional qualification. Researcher applied one way analysis of variance. The table 3.0 reported that the p- value of one way ANOVA is 0.00562 which indicates that the calculated value of F- ratio (5.25) is greater than tabulated value (4.66) at 0.01 level of significance therefore null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference in the multiple intelligence of primary school teachers in regard to their professional qualification’ is being rejected. It means, the professional qualifications fluctuate the level of multiple intelligence of primary school teachers. The reason behind this finding that the admission criteria and procedures in each training course are different.

According to **Garret, H.E. (2008)** when ANOVA exhibits significant difference then t – test would be applied therefore researcher used t-test to find out significance difference between professional qualifications of primary school teachers.

Table 3.1: Comparison between B.T.C. and Distance B.T.C. primary school teachers on their Multiple Intelligence score

MI Score PQ	Size of Sample	Mean	Standard Deviation	Critical ratio
B.T.C.	133	300.67	19.76	2.69 *
Distance B.T.C.	74	291.87	24.16	

* Significant at 0.01 level of significance.

Table 3.1 explores the comparison between B.T.C. and Distance B.T.C. teachers of primary school on multiple intelligence. Researcher applied t- test for data analysis. The table 3.1 reported that the calculated value of critical ratio is 2.69 which greater than the tabulated value 2.59 of degree of freedom (205)at 0.01 level of significance therefore null hypothesis ‘there is no significant difference in the multiple intelligence of B.T.C. and Distance B.T.C. teachers of primary schools’ is being not accepted. The mean score of B.T.C. teachers (300.67) was higher than the Distance B.T.C. (291.87) teachers of primary school. It indicates that B.T.C. teachers of primary school have higher level of multiple intelligence in comparison to those teachers who have a distance BTC degree.

Table 3.2: Comparison between Distance B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary schools on their Multiple Intelligence

MI Scores PQ	Size of Sample	Mean	Standard Deviation	Critical ratio
Distance B.T.C.	74	291.88	24.16	2.98*
B.Ed.	191	301.71	23.99	

* Significant at 0.01 level of significance.

Table3.2discloses the level of multiple intelligence of Distance B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary school. For the statistical verification of hypothesis t-test is applied. The table 3.3 reported that the critical ratio 2.98> table value 2.59 of df (263) at 0.01 level of significance therefore null hypothesis, “there is no significant difference in the multiple intelligence of Distance B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary schools” is being rejected. The researcher concluded that the difference in level of multiple intelligence of primary school teachers is significant. The mean(291.87) of Distance B.T.C. teachers of primary school was found

lower comparatively B.Ed. teachers of primary school (301.71). It means B.Ed. teachers of primary school have high level of multiple intelligence in comparison to Distance BTC.

The admission, classes, internship and evaluation process are different in formal education in comparison of informal system of education because distance B.T.C. is the part of informal education.

Table-3.3: The Comparison of Multiple Intelligence among B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary school.

M I Scores PQ	Size of Sample	Mean	Standard Deviation	Critical ratio
B.T.C.	133	300.67	19.76	0.43
B.Ed.	191	301.71	23.99	

Table 3.4 elicit the level of multiple intelligence of B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary school. For the statistical treatment of hypothesis t-test is applied. This table revealed that the critical ratio 0.43 is less than the table value 1.97 of at 0.05 level of significance therefore the null hypothesis, “there is no significant difference in the multiple intelligence of B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers of primary schools’ is being accepted. It was found that B.T.C. and B.Ed. Teachers of primary school have equivalent level of multiple intelligence.

Table 4.0: Comparison on Teaching Competency of primary school teachers in relation to their teaching experience.

TC Scores TE	Size of Sample		Mean	Standard Deviation	
0-2 Years	84		203.33	20.03	
3-5 Years	73		201.19	19.22	
6-10 Years	82		203.28	17.43	
More than 10 years	159		203.07	18.53	
Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean of squares	F ratio	p value
Treatment between groups	242.01	3	80.67	.23	0.87549
Error	138802.32	394	352.29		
Total	139044.33	397	432.96		

Table 4.0 presents scores and ANOVA summary of teaching competency of primary school teachers in reference to their teaching experience. For the testing of null hypothesis researcher applied one way ANOVA. This table 4.0 depicted that the p-value of F-ratio is .87459 which indicates $p < 0.05$ therefore the null hypothesis 'there is no significant difference in the teaching competency of primary school teachers with regard to their teaching experience' is being accepted. It means teaching experiences of primary school teachers have no impact on Multiple Intelligence. The findings of **Singh (2015) and Pratibha (2017)** support the findings of this study but **Mishra (2017) and Parveen & Shrivastava (2020)** found contradictory result in their study. They found significant difference in teaching competency in terms of teaching experiences. The cause behind these findings can be effects of in-service trainings and similar working conditions in all primary schools because all primary schools follow rules and regulations of district level authority (BSA).

Table-5: Comparison of multiple intelligence of primary school teachers in terms of their teaching experience.

MI Scores TE	Size of Sample (N)		Mean	Standard deviation	
0-2 Years	84		304.57	22.07	
3-5 Years	73		297.49	21.02	
6-10 Years	82		296.69	18.78	
More than 10 years	159		299.27	25.78	
Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom	Mean of squares	F ratio	p value
Treatment between groups	3107.51	3	1035.83	1.98	0.116419
Error	205897.56	394	522.58		
Total	209005.07	397	1558.41		

Table 5.0 mentions scores and one way ANOVA summary table of Multiple Intelligence among primary school teachers in relation to their teaching experience. To check significance difference, researcher used one way analysis of variance. The table 4.1 depicted that the F-ratio is 1.98 which is less than table value of f-test therefore null hypothesis 'there is no significant difference in the Multiple Intelligence of primary school teachers in relation to their teaching experience' is being accepted. It means, the multiple intelligence of primary school teachers is not affected by the teaching experience.

Conclusion

Researchers draw following conclusions on the analysis of data.

1. There is no significant difference found in the teaching competency of primary school teachers in relation to their professional qualification.
2. The significant difference is found on the level of multiple intelligence of primary school teachers in regard to their professional qualification. After further analysis the significant difference in multiple intelligence is found within the groups of (B.T.C. and Distance mode B.T.C.) and (Distance mode B.T.C. & B.Ed.) primary school teachers. The level of multiple intelligence of B.T.C. and B.Ed. teachers is higher than Distance mode BTC teachers of primary school but there is no significant difference found in multiple intelligence of B.T.C. & B.Ed. teachers.

3. There is no significant difference was found in teaching competency and multiple intelligence of primary school teachers in terms of their teaching experience. So we can say that teaching experience does not affect the teaching competencies.

References

- Armstrong, (1994). *Multiple Intelligences in the Classroom*. Virginia: ASCD.
- Armstrong, T., (2009). *Multiple intelligences in the classroom*, 3rd edition. Alexandria, VA: Association for Supervision and Curriculum Development.
- Arora, S. & Gangwar, D.V. (2022) *Construction of Multiple Intelligence Scale*, *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language*. 10(49)
- Aslani, R. M. (2010) *the effectiveness of remedial strategy in light of Multiple Intelligences in developing geometry achievement and attitudes toward geometry among 2nd preparatory Slow learners in Jeddah Government, unpublished Ph.D., Thesis. Females faculty of Education Ieddoh Saudi Arabia.*
- Ayesha, B. & Khurshid, F. (2013) *The Relationship of Multiple Intelligence and Effective Study Skills with Academic Achievement Among University Students*. *Global Journal of Social Science Linguistic and Education*, 13.1(1) online retrieved on 01.01.22. from https://globaljournals.org/GJHSS_Volume13/3-The-Relationship-of-Multiple-Intelligence.pdf
- Best, J.W. & Khan, J.V. (2016). *Research in Education 10th Ed*. New Delhi, PHI Learning Private India ISBN: 8120335635, 9788120335639.
- Chinliansiana, H. (2022). *A study on the General Teaching Competency of Pre-service Student-teachers of DIET, Lunglei; Mizoram*. online assessed on 03.06.2022 from the website <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360049526>
- Deslandes, R., Fournier, H. & Rosseau, N. (2005) *Relation of trust between parents and teacher of children in elementary school in Raquel Amya Marlines- Gonzalez, ma del hear perez herrero and Biarritz Rodriquez Ruiz (213-232) family school community partnership. Merging into social development Oviedo \ spear: Group Sm.*
- Dey, D., Chanda, B. & Heald, T. (2015). *Applicability of Teacher's Competency at Elementary Level: A study on Jalpaiguri District*. *International Research Journal of Interdisciplinary & Multidisciplinary Studies (IRJIMS)*. 1(3) 23- 29 online retrieved 03.3.2021 from <https://oaji.net/articles/2015/1707-1438673686.pdf>
- Gangwar, D.B. & Arora, S. (2022). *A Study of Family Environment and Multiple Intelligence of Secondary Students*, *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science & English Language*. 10(71)
- Gardner, H. (1983). *Frames of minds: The theory of Multiple Intelligences*. New York.
- Gardner, H. (1993). *Multiple Intelligences – the theory in Practice* New York: Basic Books
- Gardner, H., 2001. *The Three Faces of Intelligences*. online available at <http://howardgardner01.files.wordpress.com/2012/06/the-three-faces-of-intelligence1.pdf> assessed on 2.1.2021.
- Johnson, B. & Christensen, L. (2012). *Educational Research 4th Ed*. Delhi: SAGE Publication India Pvt. Ltd. New Delhi.
- Kaur, M & Talwar, A. (2014). *Multiple intelligence of secondary school teachers in relation to emotional intelligence*, *International Journal of Learning, Teaching educational research* 3 (1) 83-90. online available at and retrieved

- on.1.1.2021from<https://www.ijlter.org/index.php/ijlter/article/view/67>
- Mishra, S. (2017). *Teaching Competencies among Secondary School Teachers of Sikkim. Pedagogy of Learning: International Refereed Journal of Education.* 3 (1), 17-26.
- Nulhakim, L., & Berlian, L. (2020). *Investigation of multiple intelligence of primary school students. Jurnal Inovasi Pendidikan IPA, 6(1), 101-113.* doi:<https://doi.org/10.21831/jipi.v6i1.29478>
file:///C:/Users/dell/Downloads/29478-89256-1-PB.pdf
- National council of Educational research and professional (NCERT, 2009) *Comprehensive evaluation of centrally scheme on reconstructing andreorganization of Teacher Education's A Report National Council of Educational research and professional New Delhi. India.*
- New Mexico (USA) Public Education Department (2012) *professional Development framework.* Retrieved from <http://www.teachrm.org>. on
- Pratibha (2017). *Teaching competency of primary school teachers and their relation with sex and educational qualification, Abhinav National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Arts & Education, Volume 6, Issue 1, ISSN-2277-1182*
- Prada M.D.M.& Gonzalez. J (2014). *Competence based multiple learning path on the road of implementation truing. Journals for higher Education 2(1) 107-128.*
- Passi, B.K. & Lalita, M.S. (2011). *General multiple intelligence scale Agra, National Psychological Research cell.*
- Parveen ,S. & Shrivastava,N.(2020). *A study of teaching competency of upper primary school teachers of Central and State Government schools. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) 8,(10).1636-1642*
- Shukla, S.(2014).*Teaching Competency, professional commitment journal of Research method in Education,4(3) 44-64.*
- Sivakumar, D. & Arunachalam, N. (2012). *Relational studies on multiple intelligence and achievement in science among high school students. Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary studies, 1(3) online available on www.srjis.com*
- Singh, P. (2015). *Madhayamik star ke sikshakon ki shikshan dakshata ka unke atma pratyay va sanmvegatamk buddhi ke sandarbh me adhyayan unpublished thesis; Banaras Hindu University Banaras online assessed on 12.1.2020from <https://shodhganga.inflibnet.ac.in:8443/jspui/handle/10603/274837>*